

Collaborative networks and international research publication practices: metrics, impact and implications for researchers' education and training

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**Co-funded by
the European Union**

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Context and rationale

- Scientific collaboration drives scientific productivity and impact (Abramo et al., 2019; Hâncean et al., 2021; Hyland, 2025)
- Previous research:
 - Quantitative analyses of collaboration networks (e.g. Álvarez et al., 2015; Sarigöl et al, 2014)
 - Quan/qual studies on how researchers communicate research (e.g. Diao, J. (2021, 2023; Hyland and Zou, 2022; Thelwall, 2017)
- We connect two dimensions
 - The social dimension → How scientists collaborate in research publications
 - The textual dimension → How scientists use language when writing coauthored papers

Aim of the study and research questions

- Why **two** dimensions?
 - Quantitative: co-authorship networks → collaboration structure → visibility & influence.
 - Qualitative: linguistic analysis → communicative strategies
- The Science of Science → are classical metrics enough?
- We propose a combined lens for visibility and professional growth
- Questions
 - How do network properties shape researcher visibility?
 - How do linguistic features of titles relate to impact?
 - How can these findings inform researcher training?

Data overview and scope

- DILAN (Digital Science and Communication Training for EU scientists) Project → 11 EU researchers from STEM fields
- Publication data extracted from Web of Science API
 - Researcher by researcher
 - Python script
- Fields used:
 - authors with their affiliations → base for network analysis
 - title
 - year of publication
 - journal info → name, rank, JCR impact by year
- Resulting dataset: ~1,300 authors, 435 publications in total

Method: pipeline

Method: data curation and disambiguation

- Classic problem in bibliographic repositories → inconsistent naming in bibliographic records
- 3SA method used (Muñoz-Jordán et al., 2025).
- Similar method for researchers.
- The result is an unified and accurate author-institution dataset

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Method. Network construction

- Researchers are represented as nodes
- Edges are co-authorships between researchers
 - 2 researchers are linked if they have co-authored a least a publications
- **Kampal Research tool** → Python + igraph + Web Platform
- Visual layout → Fruchterman-Reingold

Method: network and metrics analysis

- Networks

- Alternative weightings: publication count, quartile, excellence (top-decile journals).
- Aggregation by country/city tested.
- Global structure remained consistent → robust results.
- JCR-weighted version chosen for clarity.

- Metrics

- Clustering
- Assortativity
- Modularity
- Degree centrality
- Betweenness
- PageRank

Results: global network

- 435 publications, 1,300 nodes, ~8000 links
- Clustering: 0.29
- Assortativity: -0.066
- Modularity: 0.73
- Avg. path length: 2.27 → max: 4 → small world property
- Half of the nodes are in the giant component
- Structural insights:
 - Eleven focal researchers occupy distinct communities.
 - Some act as bridges across disciplines.
 - Highlights diversity of collaboration.

Results: selection of case studies

Researcher	Output	Dispersion	Bridge	Stability
A. M. Geer	Medium	Low	No	High
C. Madore	High	Medium	Yes	High
F. Alla	High	High	Yes	High
K. Kelfoun	Medium	High	Partial	Low

Results: Ana M. Geer

- Medium output; high clustering (0.57).
- Few, stable long-term ties.
- Cohesive core network.

Results: Charlotte Madore

- Second in degree (264.8); eight clusters.
- Bridge through Oleg Butovsky.
- Distributed, multi-community structure.

Results: François Alla

- Hub-and-spoke structure (degree 633.9).
- Betweenness = 1.0 → central integrator.
- 20 collaboration clusters.
- Low clustering → hierarchical configuration.

Results: Karim Kelfoun

- Moderate output, high PageRank (0.45).
- Bridges volcanology sub-networks.
- Links with peripheral but active collaborators.

Results: a comparative

- High modularity (0.73) in global network → clear community structure.
- Individual networks show heterogeneity:
 - Geer = dense, low dispersion (cluster 0.57)
 - Madore = interconnected multi-hub (modularity 0.39)
 - Alla = centralized hub (modularity 0.53)
 - Kelfoun = hybrid hub bridge (0.48)
- Different configurations → complementary pathways to visibility.

Insights from co-authorship network analysis

- Productivity alone \neq visibility.
- Centrality and position within the network are more important.
- Four archetypes: hub, integrator, connector, cohesive core.
- Bridges between communities enhance impact and resilience.
- Supports previous findings (e.g. Bordons et al., 2015; Newman, 2001; Sarigöl et al., 2014).

Method: linguistic analysis

- Expand network analysis with the analysis of article titles.
- Examining lexical and syntactic complexity is one way to understand linguistic complexity (Stanisz et al., 2019; 2024).
- Lexical complexity
 - Moving Average Type/Token Ratio (MATTR) and Measures of Textual Lexical Diversity (MTLD)
 - measures of lexical sophistication (word frequency, collocations) and lexical density (content/function words)
- Syntactic complexity
 - Title length; single/multipart structures; declarative/interrogative; use of simple/complex noun phrases; phrasal/clausal embeddings, the use of dependent clauses per T-unit or clausal subordination; discourse style features
- Purpose: assess “**communicative efficiency**” and variation across networks

Examples of lexical and grammatical complexity in titles

Organoruthenium complexes containing phosphinodicarboxamide ligands

Apolipoprotein E4 impairs the response of neurodegenerative retinal microglia and prevents neuronal loss in glaucoma .

Comparative effectiveness of rosuvastatin vs simvastatin in primary prevention among new users A cohort study in the French national health insurance database

Growth and collapse of the 2018 - 2019 lava dome of Merapi volcano .

Adjective

Adverb

Conjunction

Determiner

Noun

Number

Preposition

Pronoun

Verb

Results and implications of title choices

- Titles act as filters and visibility tools.
- Effective titles = informative + concise + persuasive.
 - Specific title properties (e.g., high level of lexical diversity, i.e. remarkably varied vocabulary; high lexical density; preference for phrasal structures; features of grammatical compression and grammatical elaboration)*
- A structured network presence, paired with effective, measured language in titles, significantly contributes to the impact and perceived significance of the research.
- Structure enables communication; communication boosts visibility.
- Differences reflect disciplinary conventions.
- Pedagogical implication: train researchers to craft impactful titles.

* Ruiz, G., Divasón, J., & Pérez-Llantada, C. (2025, noviembre 16). The dual ecology of academic success: connecting co-authorship networks to article title properties: Why titles matter?. 48th International Conference of the Spanish Association for Anglo-American Studies (AEDEAN 2025), Vitoria, Gasteiz (Spain). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17622700>

Erasmus + Digital Language and Communication Training for EU Scientists (DILAN) co-funded by the European Commission (2022-1-ES01-KA220-HED-000086749).

This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

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Instituto Universitario de Investigación
**de Biocomputación y Física
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Universidad Zaragoza

PID2023-148454NB-I00 MCIN/AE